

OPPORTUNITIES TO USE DIGITAL STRATEGIES IN BUSINESS

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Abstract. *The article reveals the role and importance of digital strategy in the market-oriented activities of enterprises. Digital economy is a socio-economic system in the form of electronic, internet, network and virtual economy aimed at increasing the efficiency of production of goods and providing services by means of digital data, which is directly related to the development of information and communication technologies of economic activity, analysis issues are explained.*

Keywords: *Digital, economy, business, electronic, internet, network, technology, innovation, development, social networks, strategy consumers.*

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В БИЗНЕСЕ

Аннотация. *В статье раскрываются роль и значение цифровой стратегии в рыночно-ориентированной деятельности предприятий. Цифровая экономика – социально-экономическая система в форме электронной, интернет-, сетевой и виртуальной экономики, направленная на повышение эффективности производства товаров и оказания услуг посредством цифровых данных, что напрямую связано с развитием информационно-коммуникационных технологий. хозяйственной деятельности, разъяснены вопросы анализа.*

Ключевые слова: *Цифра, экономика, бизнес, электроника, интернет, сеть, технологии, инновации, развитие, социальные сети, стратегия потребителей.*

The impact of digital technologies is felt both globally and locally. The digital economy is a rapidly growing part of the global economy as a combination of new productions. New technologies have a transformative effect on some aspects of the activities of well-established business entities, which mainly consists of replacing working mechanisms - communication tools or industrial machines with digital or digital mechanisms, as well as further modernizing them.

The growth of the digital economy is related to the growth of a number of markets directly related to digital and mobile technologies. At the current stage of technology development and the current state of the markets, the digital economy should be considered not as a goal, but as a means of increasing the efficiency of economic activity. The modern digital economy offers new business models and emphasizes the need to change governance mechanisms to reflect the changing reality.

Market impact through the use of digital technologies is often created by companies that can combine digital technologies and physical resources to improve their performance.

Choosing one of the appropriate models of digital technology in business, i.e., process, network, technological models, allows to specify the work to be done in business enterprises, to increase efficiency consistently and through a clearly defined action plan. Therefore, in order to implement digital technologies in business in enterprises, the following is suggested:

1. Having a team of highly qualified workers with the necessary competence in the work process;
2. Development of a set of methods, techniques and measures that allow for the most effective combination with innovative work tools and objects, taking into account the current conditions and time;
3. Based on the need to increase the pace of digitalization of production, it is necessary to establish active cooperation with interested organizations and enterprises, specialized higher education institutions, vocational schools.

The effectiveness of using digital technologies in the digital economy and business shows that it is developing simultaneously in a wide range of areas and is usually not built by a limited number of companies, even if they are given special powers and resources. Therefore, the main role of the use of digital technologies in the digital economy and business should be occupied by private businesses with a strong entrepreneurial and innovative approach, and the state should deal with creating infrastructure and conditions for private initiative.

Digital strategy is a form of strategic management and business approach to the development of digital technologies.

A digital strategy as part of a business strategy is only effective if it is relevant to the overall corporate strategy.

A sound digital strategy, like a traditional business strategy, focuses on making and executing the right investment decisions to maximize competitive advantage, growth, profits and business value.

Today, any company needs to take advantage of digital technologies by developing a digital strategy. Such a strategy should consist of a combination of information, digital technologies and physical resources that will allow to increase human efficiency. Failure to do so will reduce the company's competitiveness. For example, digital companies in the US are leading traditional companies in terms of products, services, business model innovation and revenue growth.

Although digital strategy and corporate strategy are still at the center of discussions, we believe that a company's digital strategy should become the core of its corporate strategy.

A digital strategy can work, at least when it is combined with a corporate strategy.

In short, a digital strategy for companies is not an alternative choice, but a requirement for any company that wants to be competitive in its market.

What is the relationship between generic and digital strategies?

Digital strategies can be divided into digitalization and digital transformation:

- digitization strategy is a functional strategy because it affects the change of individual processes;
- digital transformation strategy is a corporate strategy, because it is generally related to the change of business, the formation of a new business model.

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